

α -Aminoisobutyric acid: A single amino acid chain inverter

Rajib Sarkar

Department of Chemistry, Muragachha Government College, University of Kalyani, Nadia-741 235,
West Bengal, India

E-mail: rajibsarkar.org@gmail.com

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A tripeptide, Boc-(L)-Leu(1)-Aib(2)-(L)-Leu(3)-OMe, **1** containing α -aminoisobutyric acid and a coded amino acid was synthesized and fully characterized. Then, conformational preference of the tripeptide was studied. The highly hydrophobic peptide adopts bend conformation like a helix. But there is no intramolecular hydrogen bonded regular β or γ turn. The X-ray crystallography of the tripeptide shows that the peptide has a helical conformation with consecutive five members N-H...N hydrogen bonded turn. The single amino acid chain inverter forms a 2 \rightarrow 1 N-H...N hydrogen bonds and helical structure which are rare element of proteins.

Keywords: α -Aminoisobutyric acid, non-proteinogenic, helix, turn, chain-Inverter.

Introduction

α -Aminoisobutyric acid (AIB) is a 2-methyl derivative of alanine. In laboratory, it can be prepared from acetone cyanohydrin, by reaction with ammonia followed by hydrolysis¹. But large scale synthesis can be achieved by the selective hydroamination of methacrylic acid. It is a non-proteinogenic amino acid found in some lantibiotics and antibiotics of fungal origin like alamethicin. However, it is rare in nature. AIB has lots of biological activities. It has the compatibility with ribosomal elongation of peptide synthesis². It is proposed as protective factor against metabolic disorder since it can induce brown fat function³. AIB is a strong helix inducer in peptides. Oligomers of AIB generally form 3₁₀-helices.

Helices are one of the most abundant (26%) secondary structures observed in proteins⁴. Helices are very well studied structural elements among the protein structural elements. The α -helix and 3₁₀-helix are frequently found in proteins⁵. Mimicking helical structures with non-natural amino acids is highly interesting to understand the protein folding, tertiary and quaternary structures which largely depends on intramolecular and intermolecular interactions between properly placed amino acid side chains⁶. Significant research has been done in this regard using β - and γ -peptides which can adopt

diverse helical conformations⁷. Even, linear arrays of side chains at defined intervals has been used to mimic the projection of i, i+4, and i+7 residues from one face of an α -helix⁸. Gellmann and coworkers have reported helical structures from β -peptide and α,β -hybrid peptide backbone⁹. Balaram and coworkers have reported a 9-helix from peptide containing gabapentin¹⁰. Huc and coworkers have reported the α,δ -hybrid peptide which adopts a conformation with linear arrays of proteinogenic side chains¹¹. Gopi and coworkers have reported the 12-helix from α,γ -hybrid peptide by reduction of peptides with unsaturated amino acids¹². Intriguing by the previous knowledge, we wanted to fabricate peptide based unusual helical structure with minimum amino acid residues. Herein, we present a tripeptide Boc-(L)-Leu(1)-Aib(2)-(L)-Leu(3)-OMe **1**, containing α -aminoisobutyric acid and a coded amino acid. The conformational preferences of the peptide have been studied in solution using different spectroscopic techniques. The highly hydrophobic peptide adopts bend conformation like a helix. But no intramolecular hydrogen bonded regular β or γ turn was observed. The X-ray crystallography of the tripeptide shows that the peptide has a helical conformation along b-axis with consecutive five member N-H...N hydrogen bonded turn¹³. Thus, AIB acts as a single amino acid chain inverter forming a 2 \rightarrow 1 N-H...N hydrogen bonds and helical structure.

Experimental

Peptide synthesis:

Peptide **1**, was synthesized (Fig. 1) by conventional solution phase methods as reported in literature¹⁴. The Boc group was used for N-terminal protection and the C-terminus was protected as a methyl ester. Deprotection of methyl ester was performed using saponification method. Couplings were mediated by dicyclohexylcarbodiimide/N-hydroxybenzotriazole (DCC/HOBt).

Fig. 1. Reactions and conditions: (a) DCC, HOBt, dry DCM, 273 K, Et₃N, 48 h, 70–80% (b) 1(N) NaOH, MeOH, 300 K, 12 h, HCl, 90–95%.

All of the intermediates were characterized by 500 MHz Brüker Advance, 400 MHz Jeol, ¹H NMR and mass spectrometry. The final compound was fully characterized by 500 MHz, 400 MHz ¹H NMR spectroscopy, ¹³C NMR spectroscopy (125 MHz, 100 MHz), mass spectrometry. Finally, the tripeptide was characterized by single-crystal X-ray crystallography.

Spectroscopic study:

NMR experiments:

All NMR studies were carried out on a Brüker Avance 500 MHz spectrometer at 298 K. The compounds concentrations were in the range 1–10 mmol in CDCl₃ and (CD₃)₂SO.

FT-IR spectroscopy:

All reported solid-state FTIR spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum RX1 spectrophotometer with the KBr disk technique.

Mass spectrometry:

Mass spectra were recorded on a Q-ToF Micro YA263 high resolution (Waters Corporation) mass spectrometer by positive mode electro spray ionization.

X-Ray diffraction study:

Intensity data were collected with Mo-K α radiation using Bruker APEX-2 CCD diffractometer. Data were processed using the Bruker SAINT package and the structure solution and refinement procedures were performed using SHELX97¹⁸. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The data has been deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre with reference CCDC 208708.

Results and discussion

The tripeptide, **1** was designed with the assumption that the helicogenic α -aminoisobutyric acid will retain the conformational preferences and the hydrophobic L-leucine residues will help to adopt helical conformations. The synthesized compounds were purified and characterized by ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, FT-IR, mass spectrometry (MS) and X-ray Diffraction study.

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy is an excellent technique to study the secondary structure of peptides. The region 1800–1500 cm⁻¹ is important for the stretching band of amide I, the bending peak of amide II and the hydrogen bonded urethane groups¹⁵. Another informative frequency range is 3500–3200 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the N-H stretching vibrations of peptides.

Fig. 2. The FT-IR spectra of the tripeptide.

An intense band at 3313 cm⁻¹ was observed for the reported tripeptide, indicating the presence of strongly hydro-

gen-bonded NH groups. The characteristic IR absorption bands at about 1509, 1665 and 1702 cm^{-1} for peptide **1** suggest that the peptides have no distinguished structure, such as the typical parallel or anti parallel β -sheet structures. The FT-IR study shows that the peptides molecules are strongly intermolecularly hydrogen bonded in the solid state (Fig. 2).

The molecular conformation of the peptide **1** in the crystal presented in Fig. 3, reveals that though the peptide contains a helicogenic α -aminoisobutyric acid (AIB) at central position, the peptide does not form any intramolecular hydrogen bonded β -turn structure, which is very regular for most of the AIB containing peptides.

Fig. 3. The solid state conformation the tripeptide.

The torsion angles values of the majority of the constituent amino acid residues are fall within the helical region of the Ramachandran map. Interestingly, the torsion angle around the Leu(1) ($\phi_1 = -76.6^\circ$, $\psi_1 = 27.1^\circ$) and Aib(2) ($\phi_2 = 60.2^\circ$, $\psi_2 = 48.8^\circ$) appears to play a critical role in dictating the overall helical backbone structure of peptide **1**. The torsion angles are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Important torsion angles of the tripeptide

ϕ_1	ψ_1	ϕ_2	ψ_2	ϕ_3	ψ_3
-76.6	27.1	60.2	48.8	-81	-175.2

There are two intramolecular N-H...N hydrogen bond¹⁶ that helps single amino acid chain inverter that can form a 2 \rightarrow 1 hydrogen bonds. Fig. 4 shows the consecutive five members N-H...N hydrogen bonded turns in peptide **1** and the helix appear along crystallographic b direction due to consecutive single amino acid chain inverter. The leucine side chains are in the same side of the helix.

Fig. 4. (a) The 2 \rightarrow 1 hydrogen bonds of peptide, **1** showing single amino acid chain inverter. (b) The top view showing the helix hollow.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the conformational preferences of a tripeptide containing -leu-aib- moiety has been reported. The highly hydrophobic peptides adopt bend conformations like a helix. But there is no intramolecular hydrogen bonded regular β or γ -turn observed. The X-ray crystallography of the tripeptide¹⁷ shows that the peptide has a helical conformation with consecutive five member N-H...N hydrogen bonded turn. The single amino acid chain inverter forms a 2 \rightarrow 1 N-H...N hydrogen bonds and helical structure which are rare element of proteins. The results presented here may foster new studies on designer foldamer with advance application.

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 17. Crystallographic data: Peptide **1**: C₂₂H₄₁N₃O₆, Mw = 443.59, orthorhombic, space group P212121, *a* = 9.7888(6), *b* = 10.3851(8), *c* = 24.5035(17) Å, *V* = 2491.0(3) Å³, *Z* = 4, *dm* = 1.183 Mg m⁻³. Intensity data were collected with Mo-K α radiation at room temperature using Bruker APEX-2 CCD diffractometer. Data were processed using the Bruker SAINT package and the structure solution and refinement procedures were performed using SHELX97¹⁸. The non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic thermal parameters. The hydrogen atoms were included in geometric positions and given thermal parameters equivalent to 1.2 times those of the atom to which they were attached. The final R values were for peptide **1**: R1 = 0.0927 and wR2 = 0.2199 for 4063 data with *I* > 2 σ (*I*). The data was deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre with reference number CCDC 208708.
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